

**THE ESSENCE AND IMPORTANCE OF MARKET SEGMENTATION IN
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Abstract: Marketing is an effective tool and basis of small business and entrepreneurship in decision-making and its development. This article talks about the importance of marketing in small business and entrepreneurial activities.

Keywords: Macrosegmentation, Entrepreneurship, market segmentation, marketers, market regions, countries, instruments, consumer demand.

Market segmentation is important in the marketing management system, and the study of market demand or, in the words of marketers, "consumer analysis" is the first step in the analysis of the market situation. It is divided into three components:

- market segmentation;
- study the reasons for consumer demand;
- identify unmet needs.

Market segmentation is a stratified approach to demand satisfaction, based on the use of various criteria for dividing consumers into groups that have different demands according to the type, quality, and quantity of the product, that is, the market is not a homogeneous phenomenon, but individual segments in the form of a set, in the form of a phenomenon in which a unique demand is manifested within each segment.

In the market, buyers have different requirements for a certain product, each buyer has his taste. Information about the buyer's demand, desire, need, lifestyle, and behavior in purchasing goods creates opportunities for the development and implementation of effective marketing activities. That is, market segmentation ensures that the product is offered to the customer's demand and ensures the stability of the demand for the product.

So, the behavior of customers in purchasing goods Market segmentation is the division into groups based on their characteristics, demand, and attitude to goods.

There are many aspects to choosing segmentation criteria depends on the type of goods or services, as well as the problem that the enterprise wants to solve in the market activity.

The selection criteria for industrial goods and consumer goods are very different from each

other. An optimal criterion that is very suitable for planning needs may not be suitable at all for the issues of placing the product in the market. If a certain criterion does not allow to explain the difference between buyers, then it is necessary to introduce another criterion and conduct research until these differences are clearly identified must be continued.

By segmenting the market, the business entity aims to:

- maximum consideration of consumer wishes and demands;
- competition of goods (services) and business entities ensuring tolerance;
- optimization of costs of the economic entity;
- increase the effectiveness of the marketing strategy of the business entity;
- focus on segments independent of competitors.

The main purpose of segmentation is to market behavior to learn and imagine their image (model) and future needs. The main condition for winning in today's competition is the use of new, high-quality goods and complex services, technical services, and effective sales methods. Based on these requirements, the priority type of marketing research begins with consumer research and market segmentation, because the market is not made up of the same subjects.

Market segmentation requires the most appropriate knowledge of customer requirements and customer characteristics.

Macro-segmentation envisages the division of markets by regions and countries depending on their industrialization. Micro-segmentation divides consumers of a country into groups based on more detailed criteria.

In internal segmentation, the segmentation process begins with broad consumer groups, and then gradually deepens depending on the classification of the final consumers of goods or services.

Deep segmentation involves starting with narrow consumer groups (segments) and then expanding depending on the use and application of the product. Initial segmentation is the initial stage of marketing research aimed at studying the maximum market segment.

The final segmentation is the final stage of the market analysis to organize the conditions of the market environment and the firm's capabilities.

The principles of market segmentation are:

- geographical principle;
- psychographic principle;
- demographic principle;

- the principle of behavior;
- principle of state.

The location of the market, the number and density of the population, the structure of commercial activity, the dynamics of regional development, the level of inflation, and legal restrictions are taken into account through the geographical principle.

As a result of the psychographic principle, lifestyle, type of person, and social situation are taken into account, and lifestyle is reflected in the individual's activities, interests, determination, and beliefs. The type of person can be satisfied with life, work like others, be self-confident, and have other feelings.

Demographic principles take into account the number and quality structure of families, the stage of the life cycle of the family, income level, type of occupation, education, nationality, etc., which is one of the main principles of market segmentation.

The way to purchase, user status, consumption rate, attachment level, product information, and product attitude is taken into account through the behavioral principle.

An important stage of the segmentation process is the selection of the target segment of the market. The problem of choosing a target segment is complex enough, and to solve it, it is recommended to follow the following sequence:

- change the size of the segment and its rate of change (increase, decrease);
- research of the attractiveness structure of the segment;
- determine the purpose of the segment and the organization's resources.

Segment size is characterized by its quantitative dimensions and, first of all, its capacity. To determine the capacity of the segment, it is necessary to determine the volume of goods, their total sales value in this segment, and the number of potential consumers of these goods living in the district where the market is located.

Based on the study of the market capacity, its growth dynamics, which are considered the basis for the formation of production forces and the structure of the distribution network for the sale of goods, are evaluated. It should be taken into account that the application of the results of market activity should cover the costs associated with working in the market and guarantee obtaining the planned profit.

The attractiveness of the segment and the study of the structure includes the study of the level of competition, the competitiveness of existing products, the attitude of customers, the stability of the segment's needs for the offered and existing products, the feasibility and possibility of introducing a completely new product to the market that meets the needs of

existing customers.

It is of strategic importance to determine the goals and resources of the organization necessary to achieve the goals of the segment being adopted, and to determine whether the resources of the potential opportunity are sufficient for the implementation of the current goals by the long-term goals of the organization and, accordingly, to work in the target market. It is appropriate to calculate the risk for this. Special marketing and consulting companies can be offered to calculate the risk of the foreign lot.

The following strategies can be used to select target segments:

- undifferentiated marketing strategy;
- differentiated marketing strategy;
- concentrated marketing strategy.

Practice shows that during the period of establishment and formation of market relations, many enterprises in the structure of business preferred an undifferentiated marketing strategy. This strategy focuses on the commonality of interest in the customer's needs, rather than on differences in the company's purchasing process and customer attitudes and motivations.

By developing such products and marketing programs, the firm can achieve its goal by satisfying the average mass of customers. An important factor in the success of firms using the strategy is standardization and commonality of product production. A non-differentiated marketing strategy ensures low costs in product production and sales. However, as H. Meffert noted, "this strategy is against modern marketing principles."

In the modern concept of marketing, two strategies are seen: differentiated and concentrated marketing strategy. Differentiated marketing strategy requires the company to focus its activities on several segments with goods and marketing programs specially produced for them. This strategy is consistent with the basic principle of customer-targeted marketing and a marketing program that matches the customer's motivations and understanding. This strategy fully represents the buyer's position in the market. Therefore, it is usually small compared to high sales volume and concentrated marketing strategy ensures the level of risk.

A differentiated marketing strategy requires high investment, production, and management costs, so it is necessary for large enterprises.

Product differentiation is the next opportunity to enter a different market. This is primarily based on the diversification strategy of product distribution.

A concentrated marketing strategy requires companies to focus on a profitable segment of the market, that is, one or several segments. A firm approaches this market segment with one or

more products and a targeted marketing program. By its content, this strategy corresponds to the concept of a market niche, that is, it is necessary to work in such a market segment where the product is more suitable for this firm and its delivery capabilities. A concentrated marketing strategy is more suitable for small and medium-sized enterprises since it is not necessary to have sufficient financial means to work in all market segments.

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